

FUZZY LOGIC BASED SYSTEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND BUSINESS APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

In this paper we explain some concept of fuzzy logic expert systems and its applications in business and management process. Also summarize some characteristics of fuzzy logic with the help of some real time examples which is based upon fuzzy logic applications.

Keywords

Fuzzy logic, expert systems , fuzzy TECH , fuzzification and defuzzification.

Introduction

Fuzzy logic is an approach to computing based on "degrees of truth" rather than the usual "true or false" (1 or 0) Boolean logic on which the modern computer is based. The idea of fuzzy logic was first advanced by Dr. Lotfi Zadeh of the University of California at Berkeley in the 1960s. Dr. Zadeh was working on the problem of computer understanding of natural language. Natural language (like most other activities in life and indeed the universe) is not easily translated into the absolute terms of 0 and 1. (Whether everything is ultimately describable in binary terms is a philosophical question worth pursuing, but in practice much data we might want to feed a computer is in some state in between and so, frequently, are the results of computing.).

Fuzzy logic includes 0 and 1 as extreme cases of truth (or "the state of matters" or "fact") but also includes the various states of truth in between so that, for example, the result of a comparison between two things could be not "tall" or "short" but ".38 of tallness."

Fuzzy logic seems closer to the way our brains work. We aggregate data and form a number of partial truths which we aggregate further into higher truths which in turn, when certain thresholds are exceeded, cause certain further results such as motor reaction. A similar kind of process is used in artificial computer neural network and expert systems.

Dr. Lotfi Zadeh of UC Berkeley introduced fuzzy logic in the 1960's as a means to model the uncertainty of natural language. Rather than regard fuzzy theory as a single theory, we should regard the process of "**fuzzification**" as a methodology to generalize any specific theory from a **crisp (discrete)** form to a **continuous (fuzzy)** form. Researchers

have also introduced fuzzy calculus, fuzzy differential equations, and so on.

Most applications of fuzzy logic use it as the underlying logic system for fuzzy expert systems. A fuzzy expert system is an expert system that uses a collection of fuzzy membership functions and rules, instead of Boolean logic, to reason about data. The rules in a fuzzy expert system are usually of a form similar to the following:

if u is low and v is high then w = medium

where u and v are input variables (names for known data values), w is an output variable (a name for a data value to be computed), low is a membership function (fuzzy subset) defined on u, high is a membership function defined on v, and medium is a membership function defined on w.

Most tools for working with fuzzy expert systems allow more than one conclusion per rule. The set of rules in a fuzzy expert system is known as the rule base or knowledge base.

The GIF (general inference process) works in four stages : -

1. **FUZZIFICATION**, The fuzzification comprises the process of transforming crisp values into grades of membership for linguistic terms of fuzzy sets. The membership function is used to associate a grade to each linguistic term.
2. **INFERENCE**, A fuzzy inference system (FIS) is a system that uses fuzzy set theory to map inputs (*features* in the case of fuzzy classification) to outputs (*classes* in the case of fuzzy classification) the truth-value for the premise of each rule is computed, and applied to the conclusion part of each rule. This results in one fuzzy subset to be assigned to each output variable for each rule.
3. **COMPOSITION**, all of the fuzzy subsets assigned to each output variable are combined together to form a single fuzzy subset for each output variable. In MAX composition, the combined output fuzzy subset is constructed by taking the point wise maximum over all of the fuzzy subsets assigned to variable by the inference rule (fuzzy logic OR). In SUM composition, the combined output fuzzy subset is constructed by taking the point wise sum over all of the fuzzy subsets assigned to the output variables by the inference rule.
4. **DEFUZZIFICATION**, which is used when it is useful to convert the fuzzy output set to a crisp number. There are more defuzzification methods than you can shake a stick at (at least 30). Two of the more common techniques are the CENTROID and MAXIMUM methods. In the CENTROID method, the crisp value of the output variable is computed by finding the variable value of the center of gravity of the membership function for the fuzzy value. In the MAXIMUM method, one of the variable values at which the fuzzy subset has its maximum truth-value is chosen as the crisp value for the output variable.

Various features of Fuzzy Logic

General observations about fuzzy logic:

- Fuzzy logic is conceptually easy to understand.

The mathematical concepts behind fuzzy reasoning are very simple. What makes fuzzy nice is the "naturalness" of its approach and not its far-reaching complexity.

- Fuzzy logic is flexible.

With any given system, it's easy to massage it or layer more functionality on top of it without starting again from scratch.

- Fuzzy logic is tolerant of imprecise data.

Everything is imprecise if you look closely enough, but more than that, most things are imprecise even on careful inspection. Fuzzy reasoning builds this understanding into the process rather than tacking it onto the end.

- Fuzzy logic can model nonlinear functions of arbitrary complexity.

You can create a fuzzy system to match any set of input-output data. This process is made particularly easy by adaptive techniques like ANFIS (Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference Systems), which are available in the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox.

- Fuzzy logic can be built on top of the experience of experts.

In direct contrast to neural networks, which take training data and generate opaque, impenetrable models, fuzzy logic lets you rely on the experience of people who already understand your system.

- Fuzzy logic can be blended with conventional control techniques.

Fuzzy systems don't necessarily replace conventional control methods. In many cases fuzzy systems augment them and simplify their implementation.

Linguistic variables:

While variables in mathematics usually take numerical values, in fuzzy logic applications, the non-numeric *linguistic variables* are often used to facilitate the expression of rules and facts

A linguistic variable such as *age* may have a value such as *young* or its antonym *old*. However, the great utility of linguistic variables is that they can be modified via linguistic